

Antibacterial activity of the excretory/secretory products of third instar larvae of *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca* against different bacterial strains (Sarcophagidae : DIPTERA)

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Abstract

The present study fractionate the excretory/secretory products of third instar larvae of *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca*. The results revealed the presence of 35 protein fractions with different molecular weights ranging from 4.81 to 388.13 KDa in excretory/secretory products of third instar larvae of *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca*. Only 3 protein fractions (number 22, 23 and 24) showed antibacterial activity against two strains of gram positive bacteria (*Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and against two strains of gram negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*) and these 3 protein fractions show different molecular weights. The separated protein fraction number 22 showed protein band at 41.16 KDa, separated protein fraction number 23 showed protein bands at 38.63 KDa and separated protein fraction number 24 showed protein band at 25.01 KDa. Also, the minimum inhibitory concentration was determined for each bacterial strain and it is similar in case of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* (1.95 µg/ml). The Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for *Streptococcus pneumonia* is 7.81 µg/ml and that of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 31.25 µg/ml.

Key Words: *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca*, Antibacterial activity, Gram +ve bacteria, Gram -ve bacteria.

1- Introduction

Antibiotics have been used for over 50 years in animal production for treatment of infectious diseases and as growth stimulators. However, the misuse of antibiotics has caused problems primarily related to the development of bacterial antibiotic resistance. Also, the possible accumulation of drug residues in animal products is risky for consumers and likewise contributes to the development of bacterial antibiotic resistance. These factors have resulted in a global trend to restrict the use of antibiotics in the feed industry, agriculture and veterinary medicine (Landers et al., 2012; Coyne et al., 2016). The search for alternatives to antibiotics is an urgent challenge for animal production as the maintenance of production performance as well as animal health and welfare has to be addressed adequately. Insects at all life stages are rich sources of protein, fat and many other important nutrients (Bovera et al., 2016). Reviews on the nutritive value of different insects and their meals including black soldier fly larvae, housefly maggot and pupae, mealworms, silkworm pupae, as well as locusts, grasshoppers and crickets demonstrate their potential application as an alternative protein source in the nutrition of different livestock species (Makkar et al., 2014; Sánchez-Muros et al., 2014; Józefiak et al., 2016). However, little is known about their possible secondary effects which can be related to a wide range of small

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peptides known as antimicrobial peptides (AMPs). The use of AMPs may be a promising alternative to antibiotics (Li et al., 2012; Xiao et al., 2013a,b, 2015a,b; Yoon et al., 2013, 2014; Yi et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2016). Insects have been widely used in traditional medicine in many parts of the world. In Chinese medicine, the beneficial effect of insects on different ailments has been known for over 3,000 years. Around 300 insect species are used to produce 1,700 traditional Chinese medicaments (Ratcliffe et al., 2011). The ancient medical application of insects is still explored. For example, the dried biomass of blister beetles (*Mylabris phalerata* and *M. cichorii*) containing cantharidin has been used in Chinese traditional medicine for the treatment of cancer for over 2,000 years, and studies are currently being conducted in this area (Ratcliffe et al., 2011). Cantharidin has been prescribed for numerous diseases including rabies, oedema, warts and impotence (Ratcliffe et al., 2011). It has been shown that cantharidin, or its derivatives, can destroy a variety of tumor cells *in vitro* and in animal models *in vivo* including hepatomas, leukaemia, breast cancer, melanoma and bladder or colorectal and pancreatic cancers. Additionally, some ants produce substances that promote wound healing. The most studied application, however, is the use of maggots – larvae of the housefly. Maggots eat necrotic tissues and contribute to the process of wound healing *via* a number of mechanisms. After ingestion of the necrotic tissue, their secretions promote fibroblast aggregation and tissue repairment, and finally they release antimicrobial peptides which inhibit bacterial growth in the wound (Bulet et al., 2004; Andersen et al., 2010; Ratcliffe et al., 2011).

Sarcophaga aegyptiaca belongs to the family Sarcophagidae, and are found worldwide in various environments (Roback, 1956). The adult flesh fly is approximately 13 mm long and is characterized by a black and grey striped body. The *S. aegyptiaca* feed on dead and decaying matter; however, not all species of the flesh fly consume decomposed flesh. In addition, their life cycle is temperature dependent (Woodmorappe, 1998), and their larvae goes through three instars before developing into pupae. Flies in the family Sarcophagidae are commonly known as flesh flies. They differ from most flies in that they are ovoviviparous, opportunistically depositing hatched maggots instead of eggs on carrion, dung, decaying material, or open wounds of mammals, hence their common name. Some flesh fly larvae are internal parasites of other insects (Orthoptera) (Richards and Davies, 1977).

The aim of the present study is to investigate the activity of protein fractions from ES of third larval instar of *S. aegyptiaca* against different bacterial strains and to clarify the molecular weights of these active proteins from the excretory\secretory products.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1- REARING OF INSECT

The laboratory colony of *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca* used in this study was established in the Zoology and Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Helwan University. *Sarcophaga aegyptiaca* was reared according to the method of Gabre *et al.* (2005), and identified according to Zumpt (1965).

Adults from the stock colony of *S. aegyptiaca* were kept in cages (38 × 38 × 56 cm) at 25 ± 3 °C 14 h photoperiod and 60–70% R.H. The cages were made with a wooden floor, a glass roof, and wire gauze on three of the sides. The fourth side was wooden with a circular hole fitted with a cloth sleeve to facilitate daily feeding, cleaning of the cage, and removal of eggs. Adults were supplied daily with granular sucrose, water, and pieces of liver. Water was supplied by dipping a piece of cotton as a wick in a bottle filled with water, and the liver was provided in a Petri- dish. Egg batches were removed daily and transferred to a fresh piece of chicken placed in a rearing enamel bowl (35 cm in diameter) covered with muslin secured with a rubber band. At the prepupal stage, dry autoclaved sawdust was added to the bowl as a medium for pupation. Pupae were sieved from the sawdust and transferred to adult cages described above for adult emergence.

2.2 COLLECTION OF LARVAL SECRETIONS

The ES products were collected according to modifications of reported method (Bexifield *et al.* 2004). Native excretions/secretions (nES) were collected by incubating third instars larvae of *C. megacephala* in (50,000

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larvae/ 500 ml) sterile distilled water for 1h at 30°C in darkness. The sterile liquid was siphoned from the containers and centrifuged at 10,000×g for 5 min to remove particulate material,

2.3 - FRACTIONATION OF NATIVE EXCRETIONS/SECRETIONS (NES)

Gel filtration technique was used to purify antimicrobial active compounds from the crude sample investigated. The Pharmacia column (40×2 cm) was packed by Sephadex G 150 after its soaking with phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) overnight and the samples were mixed with blue dextran and bromophenol blue dyes, loaded on the top of the column and fractions were collected (5 ml of each fraction), fractionation was performed using LPLC system (pump model MINI Puls3, detector UV/VIS-151 FC 203B, Gilson).

2.4- SCREENING ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF PROTEIN FRACTIONS

2.4.1 AGAR WELL DIFFUSION METHOD

The antibacterial activity of protein fractions was determined using agar well diffusion method (Scott, 1989). All the protein fractions were tested in vitro for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus pneumoniae* (Gram positive bacteria), *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram negative bacteria) using nutrient agar medium. Ampicillin and Ciprofloxacin were used as standard drugs for Gram positive bacteria and Gram negative bacteria. DMSO was used as solvent control. The protein fractions were tested at a concentration of 1 mg/ml against the bacterial strain.

The sterilized media was poured onto the sterilized Petri dishes (20-25 ml, each Petri dish) and allowed to solidify. Wells of 6 mm diameter was made in the solidified media with the help of sterile borer. A sterile swab was used to evenly distribute bacterial suspension over the surface of solidified media and solutions of the volume was complete to 80 ml with distilled water.

2.5 SODIUM DODECYL SULPHATE (SDS- PAGE) FOR ANTIMICROBIAL COMPOUNDS

Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was used to Separate proteins according to their molecular weight.

2.5.1 Reagent and buffers

Acrylamide Monomer Stock Solution (30%): 29.2 gm acrylamide and 0.8 gm N,N'-methylene bis-acrylamide were dissolved in 100 ml distilled water. (**Resolving Buffer:** 1.5M Tris-HCl, pH 8.8.; **Stacking Buffer:** 0.5M Tris-HCl, pH 6.8., **Resolution Buffer,** pH 8.3: 0.192 M Glycine, 0.02 Trisbase and 0.5 % SDS, **Sample Buffer:** 12 ml 1.0 m Tris-HCL pH 6.8, 8 ml glycerol, 4 ml 2-mercaptoethanol, 16 ml 10% SDS and 2 ml 0.05% bromophenol blue were made upto 80 ml with distilled water).

2.5.2 Prepration of resolving gel (10%)

The gel was prepared from: 4.0 ml distilled water, 2.5 ml resolving buffer, 3.7 ml acrylamide monomer, 100 µl 10% SDS, 50 µl 10% ammonium persulphate and 5 µl TetramethylethyleneDiamine (TEMED).

The gel was poured between the glass plates immediately and carefully overlaid with a layer of distilled water, and then the gel was kept at room temperature to polymerize.

2.5.3 Preparation of stacking gel (4%)

The gel was prepared from: 3.06 ml distilled water, 2.5 ml stacking buffer, 0.65 ml acrylamide monomer, 100 µl 10% SDS, 50 µl 10% ammonium persulphate and 5 µl TEMED. The surface of the polymerized resolving gel was rinsed with 5-7 mL of stacking gel solution. The comb was aligned in the proper position, then, the stacking gel solution was added up to 2 mm from the top edge of the resolving gel, then left for polymerization at room temperature.

2.5.4 Sample preparation

30 µl of each active fraction were mixed with 10 µl of loading sample dye. The samples were then boiled in a water bath for 2 minutes. The samples were then applied to the gel wells.

2.5.5 Running Conditions

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Electrophoresis was carried out with constant volt of 60V, The run was terminated when thebromophenol blue marker reached to the bottom of the gel. The separated proteins onpolyacrylamide gels were then stained with Coomassie blue R-250 according to the method described by **Merril(1990)**.

The electrophoresed gel was soaked in excess of staining solution for two hours, then the gelwas rinsed with distilled water and destained with excess amount of destaining solution for severaltimes until the excess stain was removed.

3-Results

The present study revealed the presence of 35 protein fractions with different molecular weights ranging from 388.13 to 4.81 KDa (Table 2). In excretory/secretory products of third instar larvae of *Sarcophagaegyptiaca*, only 3 protein fractions (number 22, 23 and 24) showed antibacterial activity against two strains of gram positive bacteria (*Streptococcus pneumonia* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and against two strains of gram negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*) (Table 3) and these 3 protein fractions show different molecular weights (Table 3). The separated protein fraction number 22 showed protein band at 41.16 KDa (Fig.1; Lane 1), separated protein fraction number 23 showed protein bands at 38.63 KDa (Fig.1; Lane 2) and separated protein fraction number 24 showed protein band at 25.01 KDa (Fig.1; Lane 3). Also, the minimum inhibitory concentration was determined (Table 1) for each bacterial strain and it is similar in case of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* (1.95 µg/ml). The Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for *Streptococcus pneumonia* is 7.81µg/ml and that of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 31.25µg/m (Table 1).

Table (1): Mean zone of inhibition in mm ± Standard deviation against two strands of gram +ve and two strands of gram –ve bacteria. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined.

Sample	Protein fraction 22	Protein fraction 23	Protein fraction 24	MIC (µg/ml)	Standard
Tested micro-organism					
GRAM +VE BACTERIA	Mean zone of inhibition in mm ± Standard deviation				Ampicillin
<i>S. pneumonia</i> (RCMB 010010)	15.6±1.5	18.6±0.63	16.2±0.58	7.81	23.8±1.2
<i>S. aureus</i> (RCMB 010028)	18.1±0.58	22.3±0.36	20.6±0.63	1.95	27.4±0.72
GRAM -VE BACTERIA	Mean zone of inhibition in mm ± Standard deviation				Ciprofloxacin
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (RCMB 010043)	15.2±0.58	16.1±1.2	16.1±0.72	31.25	20.6±1.2
<i>E. coli</i> (RCMB 010052)	18.9±1.2	23.1±0.63	19.8±1.2	1.95	23.4±0.63

Table (2): The Molecular weights of the 35 protein bands separated by SDS-electrophoresis in ES product of third larval instar of *S. aegyptiaca*.

Band number	M.WT (KDa)	Band number	M.WT (KDa)	Band number	M.WT (KDa)
1	388.13	13	97.12	25	20.00
2	379.14	14	82.22	26	19.12
3	359.25	15	70.00	27	18.33
4	340.33	16	65.15	28	17.51
5	266.41	17	50.00	29	16.31
6	195.12	18	49.12	30	14.96
7	180.26	19	48.11	31	14.31
8	150.00	20	46.13	32	13.71
9	133.11	21	43.23	33	10.00
10	128.12	22	41.16	34	5.00

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11	115.16	23	38.63	35	4.81
12	103.31	24	25.01		

Table (3): The molecular weights of 3 protein fractions that exhibit antibacterial activity against different bacterial strains.

Fraction number	M.WT (KDa)
22	41.16
23	38.63
24	25.01

Figure (1): SDS-PAGE of separated protein fractions of ES products of third larval instar of *S. aegyptiaca* compared with standard molecular weight protein leader (L); lane 1 for protein fraction number 22, lane 2 for protein fraction number 23 and lane 3 for protein fraction number 24.

4-Disscussion

In the present study, the fractionation of crude ES product of third instar larvae of *S. aegyptiaca* result is 35 protein fractions with molecular weights ranging from 388.13 to 4.81 KDa and then these protein fractions were studied against different bacterial strains such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Gram-negative bacteria), *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Gram-positive bacteria). The results revealed that only 3 protein fractions have antibacterial activity and these fractions are; fraction number 22 with molecular weight 41.16 KDa, fraction number 23 with molecular weight 38.63 KDa, fraction number 24 with molecular weight 25.01 KDa. The ES products show more antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* strain followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, respectively.

Since 2000, several research groups have been aiming to isolate and characterize such antimicrobial peptides from the ES by utilizing current methods of protein purification. The antimicrobial properties of *Lucilia sericata* larval ES and the attempts to characterize its components were independently studied in several laboratories (Jaklicet *al.*, 2008). For example, the study of Kerridgeet *al.* (2005) revealed presence of small (<1 kDa) antimicrobial factors in the secretions active against Gram positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*, including both methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and methicillin sensitive *S. aureus* (MSSA), and *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

It was reported by many authors (Mochet *al.*, 1999) the mechanism of action of maggot disinfection on wounds and they found that the excretion of maggots exhibited a strong and rapid disinfection action on *S. aureus*. Kerridgeet *al.* (2005) performed a zone of inhibition assay showing anti-bacterial activity of native

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excretory/secretory product against gram-positive bacteria such as *S. aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*, whereas **Bexfield et al. (2004)**, using a similar method and found no anti-bacterial activity. Similarly, antibacterial activity against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria including *S. aureus* and *E. coli* has further been documented but whole body extracts and the haemolymph were used instead of ES (**Huberman et al., 2007a,b**). The whole body extracts and haemolymph fractions from maggots lysed gram positive and gram negative bacteria including *P. aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and MRSA isolated from wound. Also **Taha (2015a)** reported that both ES products and whole larval homogenates of third instar larvae of *Chrysomya megacephala* have anti-bacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and no activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* this is unlike the present study on third instar larvae of *S. aegyptiaca* that showing anti-bacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain. The failure of most maggots in complete eradication of *Pseudomonas* may be related to the biofilm formation. **Van der Plaset et al. (2008)** noticed that more ES required to disrupt *P. aeruginosa* biofilms than *S. aureus* biofilms. In addition, it has been shown in vitro that *P. aeruginosa*, but not *S. aureus*, impairs maggot survival (**Andersen et al., 2010 a,b**). Together, these data are in agreement with clinical findings indicating that more maggots should be used for wounds infected with *P. aeruginosa* (**Steenvoorde and Jukema, 2004**). On the contrary to the present study, the ES products of third instar larvae of *S. aegyptiaca* show an antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa* strains and this may clarify that the ES product of third instar larvae of *S. aegyptiaca* has the ability to eradicate the *P. aeruginosa* biofilm. Also in the present study, the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *P. aeruginosa* (31.25 µg/ml) indicates that more ES required to disrupt *P. aeruginosa* biofilms than *S. aureus* biofilms (1.95 µg/ml).

The humoral immune system in insects is based on the production of induced antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) against bacterial and fungal pathogens (**Maket et al., 2010**). Antimicrobial peptides are synthesized in insect fat body and or in some blood cells, and secreted into haemolymph (**Hwang et al., 2009**). Antimicrobial peptides have mainly antifungal and antibacterial properties (**Song et al., 2010**). In insects, the constitutive AMPs are accumulated in blood cells and salivary glands. Upon a microbial challenge the AMPs get released into the haemolymph (**Cunliffe and Mahida, 2004**). In contrast, induced AMPs are synthesized in fat bodies right after the microbial infection takes place and subsequent to their biosynthesis, AMPs release into the blood stream (**Rayaproluet et al., 2010**). Meanwhile, it is noteworthy that other organs and tissues such as haemocytes might be involved in AMPs synthesis (**Reddy et al., 2004**).

In general, mechanisms of action of antimicrobial peptides are mainly depended on both the molecular characteristics of the peptide and the metabolic states of the microbial cells (**Liang and Kim, 1999**). Although mechanism of action of AMPs is a controversial subject, but the general consensus is that the majority of antimicrobial peptides, if not all, remarkably disrupt the cell membranes by making pores or channels, leading to the release of ions that may disrupt cell membrane. Consequently, the cell metabolisms may come to a halt and ultimately cell death to occur (**Melo et al., 2009**). It seems ion channel or large pore formation (due to the lack of cholesterol in microbial cell membranes especially bacteria) within pathogen cell membrane is the key mechanisms of the most AMPs (**Toke, 2005**). AMPs with the hydrophilic and hydrophobic tails manage their way through the phospholipids bilayer membranes of pathogens, leading to excess membrane permeation.

In general, maggots produce a cocktail of proteolytic and anti-microbial substances called ES products of the gut as well as salivary glands origin. In vitro examination of ES products revealed substances including serine proteases chymotrypsin and trypsin –like protease (**Thomas et al., 1999**). In general, the exact mechanism and components of the maggot's antibacterial activity are still unknown. The action of maggots secretions can increase the microcirculation and probably destroy the very complex structure of a biofilm, consequentially the bacteria become susceptible to actions of antibiotics and the immune system as well as to actions of maggots (**Mumcuoglu, 2001**). On the other hand, it can be expected that several different antibacterial components, like oligopeptides, disinfectants and low pH act synergistically (**Bexfield et al., 2004**).

Thus, it could be concluded that the different effects of maggot on Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria are mediated by different molecules and mechanisms (Van der Plaset *et al.*, 2008).

In conclusion future studies are needed to clarify the name and structure of these antibacterial compounds.

6- References

- Andersen, A.S., Sandvang, D., Schnorr, K.M., Kruse, T., Neve, S., Joergensen, B., Karlsmark, T. and Kroghfelt, K.A. (2010a). A novel approach to the antimicrobial activity of maggot debridement therapy. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 65 (8): 1646–1654.
- Andersen, A.S., Jorgensen, B., Bjarnsholt, T., Johansen, H., Karlsmark, T., Givskov, M. and Kroghfelt, K.A. (2010b). Quorum Sensing Regulated Virulence factors in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are toxic to *Luciliasericata* maggots. *Microbiology*, 156 (2): 400–407.
- Bovera F., Loponte R., Marono S., Piccolo G., Parisi G., Iaconisi V., Gasco L., Nizza A., (2016). Use of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae meal as protein source in broiler diet: Effect on growth performance, nutrient digestibility, and carcass and meat traits. *J. Anim. Sci.* 94, 639–647, <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2015-9201>
- Bexfield, A., Nigam, Y., Thomas, S. and Ratcliffe, N.A. (2004). Detection and partial characterisation of two antibacterial factors from the excretions/secretions of the medicinal maggot *Luciliasericata* and their activity against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Microbes and Infection*, 6 (14): 1297–304.
- Bulet P., Stöcklin R., (2005). Insect antimicrobial peptides: structures, properties and gene regulation. *Protein Pept. Lett.* 12, 3–11, <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929866053406011>
- Coyne L.A., Latham S.M., Williams N.J., Dawson S., Donald I.J., Pearson R.B., Smith R.F., Pinchbeck G.L., (2016). Understanding the culture of antimicrobial prescribing in agriculture: a qualitative study of UK pig veterinary surgeons. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 71, 3300–3312, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkw300>
- Cunliffe, R.N. and Mahida, Y.R. (2004). Expression and regulation of antimicrobial peptides in the gastrointestinal tract. *Journal of Leucocyte Biology*, 75: 49–58.
- Gabre, R.M., Adham, F.K. and Hsin, C. (2005). Life table of *Chrysomya megacephala* (Fabricius) (Diptera: Calliphoridae). *Acta Oecologica*, 27, 179–183.
- Huberman, L., Gollop, N., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Breuer, E., Bhusare, S.R., Shai, Y. and Galun, R. (2007a). Antibacterial substances of low molecular weight isolated from the blowfly, *Lucilia sericata*. *Medical and Veterinary Entomology*, 21: 127–131.
- Huberman, L., Gollop, N., Mumcuoglu, K.Y., Block, C. and Galun, R. (2007b). Antibacterial properties of whole body extracts and haemolymph of *Luciliasericata* maggots. *Journal of Wound Care*, (16) 3:123–127.
- Hwang, J.S., Lee, J., Kim, Y.T., Bang, H.S., Yun, E. Y., Kim, S.R., Suh, H.J., Kang, B.R., Nam, S.H., Joen, J., Kim, I. and Lee, D.G. (2009). Isolation and characterization of a defensin-like peptide (Coprinsin) from the dungbeetle, *Copristripartitus*. *International Journal of Peptides*, 2009: 1–5.
- Jaklic, D., Lapanje, A., Zupancic, K., Smrke, D. and Gunde-Cimerman, N. (2008). Selective antimicrobial activity of maggots against pathogenic bacteria. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 57: 617–625.
- Józefiak D., Józefiak A., Kierończyk B., Rawski M., Świątkiewicz S., Długosz J., Engberg R.M., (2016). Insects – a natural nutrient source for poultry – a review. *Ann. Anim. Sci.* 16, 297–313, <https://doi.org/10.1515/aoas-2016-0010>

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- Kerridge, A., Lappin-Scott, H. and Stevens, J.R. (2005).**Antibacterial properties of larval secretions of the blowfly, *Lucilia sericata*. *Medical and Veterinary Entomology*, 19: 333–337.
- Landers T.F., Cohen B., Wittum T.E., Larson E.L., (2012).** A review of antibiotic use in food animals: perspective, policy, and potential. *Public Health Rep.* 127, 4–22
- Li Y., Xiang Q., Zhang Q., Huang Y., Su Z., (2012).** Overview on the recent study of antimicrobial peptides: Origins, functions, relative mechanisms and application. *Peptides* 37, 207–215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peptides.2012.07.001>
- Liang, J.F. and Kim, S.C. (1999).** Not only the nature of peptide but also the characteristics of cell membrane determine the antimicrobial mechanism of a peptide. *Journal of peptide research*, 53: 518–522.
- Makkar H.P.S., Tran G., Heuzé V., Ankers P., (2014).** State-of-the-art on use of insects as animal feed. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 197, 1–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2014.07.008>
- Melo, M.N., Ferre, R. and Castanho, M.A. (2009).** Antimicrobial peptides: linking partition, activity and high membrane bound concentrations. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 7: 245–250.
- Merril, C.R. (1990).** Gel-staining techniques in guide to protein purification. *In: Deutscher, M.P. (Eds.), Methods in Enzymology*. Vol. 182. Academic Press, San Diego, New York, pp. 894.
- Moch, D., Fleischmann, W. and Russ, M. (1999).** The BMW (biosurgical mechanical wound treatment) in diabetic foot. *ZentralblChir*, 124: 69–72.
- Mumcuoglu, K.Y. (2001).** Clinical applications for maggots in wound care. *American Journal of Clinical Dermatology*, 2 (4): 219–27.
- Ratcliffe N.A., Mello C.B., Garcia E.S., Butt T.M., Azambuja P., (2011).** Insect natural products and processes: New treatments for human disease. *Insect Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 41, 747–769, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibmb.2011.05.007>
- Rayaprolu, S., Wang, Y., Kanost, M.R., Hartson, S. and Jiang, H. (2010).** Functional analysis of four processing products from multiple precursors encoded by a leucocin-related gene from *Manduca sexta*. *Developmental and Comparative Immunology*, 34: 638–647.
- Reddy, K., Yedery, R. and Aranha, C. (2004).**Antimicrobial peptides: premises and promises. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, 24: 536–547.
- Richards, O.W. and Davies, R.G. (1977).**Imms' General Textbook of Entomology: Volume 1, Structure, Physiology and Development Volume 2, Classification and Biology. Berlin, Springer. Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flesh_fly (accessed 20 April 2015).
- Roback, S.S. (1956).** The Evolution and taxonomy of the Sarcophaginae (Diptera, Sarcophagidae). *The Quarterly Review of Biology*, 31: 309–310.
- Sánchez-Muros M.J., Barroso F.G., Manzano-Agugliaro F., (2014).** Insect meal as renewable source of food for animal feeding: a review. *J. Clean. Prod.* 65, 16–27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.068>
- Song, K.J., Park, B.R., Kim, S. and Park, K. (2010).** Molecular characterization of anionic defensin-like peptide in immune response of silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. (Lepidoptera: Bombycidae). *Genes and Genomics*, 32: 447–453.
- Steen Voorde, P. and Jukema, G.N. (2004).**The antimicrobial activity of maggots: in vivo results. *Journal of Tissue Viability*, 14: 97–101.

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- Taha, N. (2015a).** Fractionation and purification of bioactive peptides in excretory / secretory products of third instar larvae of *Chrysomyamegacephala* (Calliphoridae: Diptera). *International Journal of Applied and Pure Science and Agriculture*, 1 (8): 129–136.
- Toke, O. (2005).** Antimicrobial peptides: new candidates in the fight against bacterial infections. *Biopolymers*, 80: 717–735.
- Thomas, S., Andrew, A.M., Hay, N.P. and Bourgoise, S. (1999).** The antimicrobial activity of maggot secretion; results of preliminary study. *Journal of Tissue Viability*, 9 (4): 127–132.
- Van der Plas, M.J., Jukema, G.N., Wai, S., Dogterom, Ballering, H.C., Lagendijk, E.L., van-Gulpen, C., van Dissel, J.T., Bloemberg, G.V. and Nibbering, P.H. (2008).** Maggot excretions/secretions are differentially effective against biofilms of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 61: 117–122.
- Wang S., Zeng X., Yang Q., Qiao S., (2016).** Antimicrobial peptides as potential alternatives to antibiotics in food animal industry. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 17, 603–614, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms17050603>
- Xiao H., Shao F., Wu M., Ren W., Xiong X., Tan B., Yin Y., (2015a).** The application of antimicrobial peptides as growth and health promoters for swine. *J. Anim. Sci. Biotechnol.* 6, 19, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40104-015-0018-z>
- Xiao H., Tan B.E., Wu M.M., Yin Y.L., Li T.J., Yuan D.X., Li L., (2013a).** Effects of composite antimicrobial peptides in weanling piglets challenged with deoxynivalenol: II. Intestinal morphology and function. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91, 4750–4756, <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6427>
- Xiao H., Wu M.M., Shao F.Y. et al., (2015b).** Metabolic profiles in the response to supplementation with composite antimicrobial peptides in piglets challenged with deoxynivalenol. *J. Anim. Sci.* 93, 1114–1123, <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2014-8229>
- Xiao H., Wu M.M., Tan B.E., Yin Y.L., Li T.J., Xiao D.F., Li L., (2013b).** Effects of composite antimicrobial peptides in weanling piglets challenged with deoxynivalenol: I. Growth performance, immune function, and antioxidation capacity. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91, 4772–4780, <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6426>
- Yi H.-Y., Chowdhury M., Huang Y.-D., Yu X.-Q., (2014).** Insect antimicrobial peptides and their applications. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 98, 5807–5822, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-014-5792-6>
- Yoon J.H., Ingale S.L., Kim J.S., Kim K.H., Lee S.H., Park Y.K., Lee S.C., Kwon I.K., Chae B.J., (2014).** Effects of dietary supplementation of synthetic antimicrobial peptide-A3 and P5 on growth performance, apparent total tract digestibility of nutrients, fecal and intestinal microflora and intestinal morphology in weanling pigs. *Livest. Sci.* 159, 53–60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2013.10.025>
- Yoon J.H., Ingale S.L., Kim J.S., Kim K.H., Lohakare J., Park Y.K., Park J.C., Kwon I.K., Chae B.J., (2013).** Effects of dietary supplementation with antimicrobial peptide-P5 on growth performance, apparent total tract digestibility, faecal and intestinal microflora and intestinal morphology of weanling pigs. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 93, 587–592, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.5840>
- Zumpt, F. (1965).** Myiasis in man and animals in the Old World. London, Butterworths. 267 pp.